

Influences of educational and personal contexts on self-efficacy and job satisfaction of public elementary school teachers

Ellaine Joy G. Eusebio¹, Philip R. Baldera¹, Aljay Marc C. Patiam¹, Charton F. Sombria²,
Jacel Ruz F. Gan², Connie G. Castillo³

¹Graduate Education and Professional Studies, Romblon State University, Romblon, Philippines

²College of Business and Accountancy, Romblon State University, Romblon, Philippines

³Limon Norte Elementary School, Department of Education, Romblon, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Enhancing teachers' performance and sense of fulfillment in their roles is essential for advancing educational quality and promoting their overall well-being. This study investigates the determinants of teachers' self-efficacy within a supportive school culture, as well as the factors influencing their job satisfaction, focusing on both educational and personal contexts among public elementary school teachers within a supportive school culture, focusing on educational and personal contexts. Utilizing a sample of 97 teachers from 13 schools in the Philippines, the research employs a causal-comparative design and surveys to gather data. The Kruskal-Wallis test results indicate no significant differences in self-efficacy and job satisfaction across age groups. The Mann-Whitney U test reveals a significant difference in self-efficacy between male and female teachers, with the latter reporting higher levels, while no significant gender differences were observed in job satisfaction. Likewise, no significant differences were found across career stages in both efficacy and satisfaction. A multivariate analysis of variance reveals that a supportive school culture has a significant impact on teachers' self-efficacy and also on their job satisfaction. These results emphasize the critical role of nurturing a supportive school environment to enhance teacher well-being and effectiveness. The study provides valuable insights and practical recommendations for improving educational quality and teacher satisfaction through targeted interventions in school culture and opportunities for career advancement.

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Corresponding Author:

Ellaine Joy G. Eusebio

Graduate Education and Professional Studies, Romblon State University

Odiongan, Romblon, Philippines

Email: eusebioellainejoy@rsu.edu.ph

1. INTRODUCTION

Teacher efficacy is a factor that influences the quality of instruction and student success, while satisfaction plays an important role in supporting teachers' well-being and retention in the profession. Self-efficacy, defined as the confidence a person has in their ability to complete tasks and reach desired objectives [1], and is not a unitary construct but varies across different domains [1]. In teaching context, teacher self-efficacy (TSE), based on Bandura's social cognitive theory, refers to teachers' beliefs in their ability to manage student learning and engagement effectively [2]. TSE plays a critical role in how teachers perceive their capabilities to perform tasks related to their profession, with implications for instructional practices, collective efforts, and persistence in the field [3], [4].

Research consistently shows that TSE is strongly linked to teaching effectiveness and student outcomes. Higher levels of efficacy in teachers are associated with more effective instructional practices and improved student learning [5], [6]. Furthermore, personal values play a major role in shaping teacher efficacy, with conservation values positively influencing self-efficacy regardless of motivation [7]. When teachers possess values of openness to change and self-transcendence, and feel a sense of self-determination, their self-efficacy is further strengthened [7]. As such, cultivating TSE is crucial for educational success, though more longitudinal and experimental research is necessary to understand its development [4].

Teachers who possess a strong sense of professional confidence are more likely to implement creative instructional methods, pursue objectives, and adjust their approaches when confronted with challenges. This not only reduces teacher burnout but also improves student motivation and achievement [4]. Confidence in one's teaching abilities plays a vital role in essential aspects such as maintaining classroom order, motivating learners, and applying effective teaching techniques. Research shows that the development of efficacy in these domains follows a phased pattern, with classroom management and student engagement efficacy developing earlier than instructional strategies efficacy [8]. Professional development initiatives that are integrated into teachers' daily work, promote inquiry-based learning, and encourage collaboration have been found to enhance teacher efficacy in various areas [9]. Notably, student engagement efficacy has been found to significantly influence preservice teachers' instructional effectiveness [10], highlighting the importance of focusing on this domain in teacher education programs.

Similarly, job satisfaction is a key element that affects both teacher performance and their overall well-being. Defined as a positive attitude towards one's work, job satisfaction fosters confidence and enthusiasm [11], [12] and has a major impact in organizational development, teacher retention, and student outcomes [13]. Theories like hierarchy of needs of Maslow and two-factor of Herzberg provide useful models for examining job satisfaction, especially within vocational college settings [11]. Teacher satisfaction can be categorized into satisfaction with the teaching profession and with the workplace environment, both of which influence teacher performance and ultimately student outcomes [14], [15].

Recent research by Khan [16] explores how approaches in managing personnel significantly influence teachers' satisfaction in Bangladesh, emphasizing the importance of supportive administrative practices. Similarly, Rajeswaran *et al.* [17] finds that effective human resource strategies can significantly enhance teacher satisfaction in secondary education. The connection between school environment and satisfaction in their roles has also been extensively studied, with supportive school cultures positively influencing job satisfaction by fostering collaboration and improving outcomes [18]. Noori [19] comparative study of teachers between public and private school offers further insights into how institutional contexts affect job satisfaction. Additionally, Guoba *et al.* [13] emphasize the complex aspects of job satisfaction and its central role in teacher well-being and efficacy.

Recent studies have specifically examined how both educational and personal contexts shape educators' confidence in their teaching capabilities and their overall contentment in the profession across various educational levels and countries. A professional school culture, characterized by collaborative inquiry and knowledge sharing, can be fostered through practices like lesson study, which has been found to enhance teacher's sense of autonomy, support, and efficacy [20]. Additionally, a school culture that promotes supportive relationships among teachers, principals, and students plays a critical role in enhancing teachers' agency in curriculum implementation [21]. Safe and supportive school environments are closely connected with increased teacher efficacy, with both distributed and instructional leadership playing a direct role in fostering these results. This kind of culture and this type of teacher relationships [22], [23], further shape the influence of leadership practices.

A healthy school culture is a crucial element in boosting teacher job satisfaction. Studies have demonstrated that such a culture not only influences teacher satisfaction but also encourages them to actively participate in professional relationships [24]. Liu *et al.* [22] further demonstrated that teachers job satisfaction benefits both directly and indirectly from shared and instructional leadership, a nurturing school climate, and cooperative engagement among educators. Abdulahi [25] also found a significant relationship between teachers' satisfaction and school culture, particularly in relation to professional growth and shared leadership practices. Moreover, Febriantina *et al.* [26] highlighted that a positive culture within the school influences teacher stress, which, in turn, significantly impacts job satisfaction. These studies collectively suggest that promoting a supportive school culture, fostering collaborative leadership, and providing professional development opportunities are essential for improving teacher job satisfaction. Managing teacher stress and encouraging professional networking also appear to contribute positively to job satisfaction.

In terms of personal context, research has shown that factors such as age, gender, and academic rank can influence both teacher efficacy and satisfaction with the job. For example, Mgaiwa [27] found that age and academic rank significantly impacted job satisfaction among university academics in Tanzania. Similarly, in Pakistan, Akhtar [28] reported that gender, age, and the nature of the institution affected teachers' job satisfaction. However, some studies found no significant differences based on these

demographic factors, suggesting that the relationship between personal context and satisfaction may vary [25]. In Nepal, Chapagain [29] observed that institutional sector and academic qualifications influenced job satisfaction, while factors like gender, age, and teaching experience did not. In Albania, Kume [30] found that teachers' gender, age, and work experience were significant factors, with female group reporting higher satisfaction than their counterparts, though school ownership (public or private) and location (urban or rural) did not significantly impact job satisfaction.

Regarding TSE, some studies have reported any significant difference based on age, gender, or years of experience [31]. However, Zizhan and Rafols [32] reported that younger teachers tend to exhibit higher self-efficacy beliefs. Educational qualifications and the grade level taught were also found to influence self-efficacy [32]. Notably, Gálvez *et al.* [33] emphasized that professional factors, such as the specific roles teachers undertake, were more closely linked to self-efficacy than demographic traits or institutional context. These results indicate that while personal dynamics like age, gender, and experience may shape teacher efficacy and satisfaction with the job, professional and contextual factors appear to have a more substantial influence. Thus, these educational and personal contexts warrant further exploration to delineate their impact on teacher confidence in their effectiveness and overall satisfaction with work.

This study, set in public elementary schools in a rural area in the Philippines, aims to dissect the interrelations between school environment and individual teacher characteristics, assessing their collective influence on teacher efficacy and satisfaction with the job. By investigating these aspects within a specific educational setting, the research intends to enrich the existing literature, providing nuanced insights and practical recommendations to enhance educational quality and teacher satisfaction. Through this endeavor, the study aspires to develop effective strategies that bolster teacher efficacy and job satisfaction, elevating student educational outcomes. It aims to examine the determinants of teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction. It examines if educational context specifically supportive school culture, and personal contexts such as age, gender, and academic rank, affect the self-efficacy as well as job satisfaction of elementary school teachers. Drawing on previous studies, the following hypotheses are proposed: i) teachers' self-efficacy significantly differ based on teachers' age, gender, and academic rank (H1); ii) teachers' job satisfaction significantly differ based on teachers' age, gender, and career stage (H2); iii) supportive school culture significantly affect teachers' self-efficacy (H3); and iv) supportive school culture significantly affect teachers' job satisfaction (H4).

Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between various independent and dependent variables in the study. This framework explores how educational and personal contexts influence teacher efficacy and satisfaction. It suggests that the culture of a school and teachers' personal attributes (age, gender, and career stage) influence their self-efficacy and satisfaction towards their job. By investigating these relationships, the study aims to offer insights into how different contexts improve teacher effectiveness and satisfaction.

Figure 1. The conceptual research framework

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study's causal-comparative research design is particularly suited to investigating the effect of educational and personal contexts on teachers' efficacy and work satisfaction. The causal approach is appropriate for identifying patterns and relationships between variables, such as the effect of supportive school culture on teacher efficacy and satisfaction. Additionally, the comparative design allows for analyzing differences between groups—such as age, gender, and career stage—without manipulating any conditions, making it a practical and ethical choice for studying real-world educational settings. This design provides

valuable insights into how demographic and environmental factors contribute to teacher well-being and effectiveness, helping inform targeted interventions in educational institutions.

2.2. Population and samples of the study

The study encompasses 13 elementary schools in a rural area in the Philippines, which collectively employ 128 teachers. The number of teachers at each school ranges from 7 to 26, reflecting different school sizes and potentially diverse school cultures and dynamics. Using the Raosoft sample size calculator, with 95% confidence level and +/-5% margin of error, the sample size derived for this study was 97. Stratified random sampling was utilized to get the number of the respondents. The researchers used a random number generator to define the respondents. A buffer list was provided in case there was an absence from the respondents when the questionnaires was administered.

2.3. Research instrument

The questionnaire for supportive school culture, consisting of 10 self-developed items, was specifically designed for this study, drawing on the works of Min [21] and Liu *et al.* [22] to develop the questions and indicators. Meanwhile, the indicators for the teacher efficacy dimensions—in classroom management (9 items), in instruction (10 items), and in student engagement (9 items)—as well as the job satisfaction components—satisfaction with the current work environment (4 items) and satisfaction with the profession (7 items)—were developed based on the suggested indicators of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) [34], with modifications to align with the study's objectives. A 4-point Likert scale ranging from 4=strongly agree to 1=strongly disagree was employed for all items. To ensure the validity of the research instrument, the questionnaire was reviewed by three experts: a department of education (DepEd) district supervisor, a master teacher, and a language expert. Their feedback and suggestions were incorporated into the final version of the questionnaire.

The researchers conducted a pre-test with 20 teachers for reliability testing, using Cronbach's alpha to assess factor reliability. The results showed that all Cronbach's alpha values were above 0.70 which indicates acceptable reliability. The teachers who participated in the pre-test were not included in the actual study sample. The researchers obtained permission to conduct the research from the office of the school division superintendent, the district supervisor, and the principals of the 13 elementary schools. When the permission was secured, the questionnaires were distributed to the respondents.

2.4. Data processing and analysis

Jamovi software and SPSS were used to analyze the gathered data. To determine the age, gender and career stage of the respondents, frequency and percentage were used. To determine the levels of the variables in this study, mean was used. To test the significant difference in efficacy and satisfaction when grouped according to teacher's profile, T-test and analysis of variance or ANOVA were used. Finally, to determine the influence of supportive school culture on teachers' efficacy and teachers' satisfaction, a multivariate analysis was used. Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents.

The respondents' profile reflects a mature and experienced group, predominantly composed of individuals aged 41–50, indicating a workforce in its peak professional years with established expertise. The limited presence of younger participants suggests fewer early-career individuals engage in the field. At the same time, the strong female majority points to a gender imbalance that may shape perspectives and experiences within the study context. Most respondents identifying as proficient rather than highly proficient imply confidence in their skills and recognition of opportunities for further growth. Overall, the profile portrays a stable, seasoned, and largely female group that combines practical experience with a continuing commitment to professional development.

Table 1. Respondents' personal and professional profile

Demographic profile		Count	% of total
Age	25-30	16	16.5
	31-40	24	24.7
	41-50	39	40.2
	50 and above	18	18.6
	Total	97	100.0
Gender	Male	13	13.4
	Female	84	86.6
	Total	97	100.0
Career stage	Proficient	86	88.7
	Highly proficient	11	11.3
	Total	97	100.0

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Significant difference in teachers' efficacy and satisfaction when grouped according to teachers' profile

Table 2 presents the level of teacher efficacy and satisfaction across different age groups, including mean values, standard deviations, and the results of test for normality. The findings indicate that self-efficacy and job satisfaction tend to decrease slightly with age, with the highest mean values observed among teachers aged 25-30 years and the lowest among those aged 50 years and above. The Shapiro-Wilk test results suggest that the data distribution is not normal, as all age groups, except for job satisfaction among teachers aged 50 years and above, show statistically significant p-values ($p < 0.05$). These results highlight potential differences in teacher perceptions across age groups, warranting further investigation through non-parametric statistical tests.

Table 2. Level of TSE and job satisfaction across age groups

Statistical measure	Age	Self-efficacy	Job satisfaction
Mean	25-30	3.73	3.55
	31-40	3.68	3.63
	41-50	3.67	3.45
	50 and above	3.47	3.42
Standard deviation	25-30	0.36	0.38
	31-40	0.41	0.45
	41-50	0.39	0.45
	50 and above	0.41	0.50
Shapiro-Wilk	25-30	<0.001	0.04
	31-40	<0.001	<0.001
	41-50	<0.001	<0.001
	50 and above	0.004	0.077

Table 3 highlights the significant differences in teacher efficacy and satisfaction across various age groups. Since the data distribution was not normal, as indicated by the normality test result, the Kruskal-Wallis test was used to compare the differences among age groups. Based on the results for self-efficacy, there is no statistically significant difference among the age groups, as the p-value exceeds the significance threshold of 0.05. Moreover, the effect size (ϵ^2) of 0.051 indicates a small effect of the grouping variable on self-efficacy. This result aligns with the findings of Mahmood *et al.* [31]. The results, although not significant, shows that younger employees show higher self-efficacy as compared to the older ones, which also aligns with the findings of Zizhan and Rafols [32]. Similarly, for job satisfaction, the Kruskal-Wallis test produced a Chi-square value of 2.92 with 3 degrees of freedom, leading to a p-value of 0.41. Again, this suggests no significant difference in job satisfaction among the groups, as the p-value is greater than 0.05. The effect size (ϵ^2) of 0.030 indicates a small effect of the grouping variable on job satisfaction. The result is consistent with the findings of Mgaiwa [27] and Chapagain [29], but contradicts Akhtar results [28].

Table 3. Kruskal-Wallis test results across age groups

Variables	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
Self-efficacy	4.85	3	0.18	0.051
Job satisfaction	2.92	3	0.41	0.030

Table 4 presents the level of efficacy and satisfaction among teachers based on their gender. Meanwhile, Table 5 highlights the significant differences in TSE and job satisfaction between males and females. Since the data distribution was not normal, as indicated by the Shapiro-Wilk test, Mann-Whitney U test was used as a non-parametric alternative to the independent samples t-test to compare gender differences. Based on the results for self-efficacy level of teachers, female teachers perceived higher self-efficacy level ($M=3.68$, $SD=0.381$) as compared to male teachers ($M=3.43$, $SD=0.443$). It was also found that the difference was significant ($p=0.04$), as the p-value is lower than 0.05. Meanwhile, for job satisfaction, it was found that females ($M=3.53$, $SD=0.449$) were also more satisfied than males ($M=3.33$, $SD=0.421$). However, the difference was not significant ($p=0.06$). The results corroborate to the findings of Chapagain [29] and contradicts the findings of Akhtar [28] and Kume [30].

Table 4. Level of TSE and job satisfaction across age groups

Variables	Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE
Self-efficacy	Male	13	3.43	3.25	0.443	0.123
	Female	84	3.68	3.86	0.381	0.042
Job satisfaction	Male	13	3.33	3.00	0.421	0.117
	Female	84	3.53	3.66	0.449	0.049

Table 5. Mann-Whitney U test results for differences in self-efficacy and job satisfaction between gender

Variables	Test used	Statistic	p
Self-efficacy	Mann-Whitney U	355	0.041
Job satisfaction	Mann-Whitney U	372	0.061

Table 6 presents the descriptive statistics of teacher efficacy and satisfaction based on career stages. Meanwhile, Table 7 highlights the significant differences in teacher efficacy and satisfaction between proficient and highly proficient teachers. Since the data distribution was not normal, the Mann-Whitney U test was again used. Based on the results for efficacy level of teachers, proficient teachers perceived higher level of self-efficacy ($M=3.65$, $SD=0.400$) as compared to highly proficient teachers ($M=3.64$, $SD=0.392$). However, it was also found that the difference was not significant ($p=0.60$), which disagrees with Gálvez *et al.* [33] findings. Meanwhile, for job satisfaction, it was found that proficient teachers ($M=3.52$, $SD=0.438$) were also more satisfied than highly proficient teachers ($M=3.41$, $SD=0.541$). However, the difference was also not significant ($p=0.537$), which opposes Mgaiwa findings [27].

Table 6. Level of TSE and job satisfaction across career stages

Variables	Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE
Self-efficacy	Proficient	86	3.65	3.84	0.400	0.0431
	Highly proficient	11	3.64	3.76	0.392	0.118
Job satisfaction	Proficient	86	3.52	3.57	0.438	0.0472
	Highly proficient	11	3.41	3.55	0.541	0.163

Table 7. Mann-Whitney U test results for career stages differences in self-efficacy and job satisfaction

Variables	Test used	Statistic	p
Self-efficacy	Mann-Whitney U	428	0.603
Job satisfaction	Mann-Whitney U	419	0.537

Examining elementary school teachers' demographics and perceptions reveals crucial insights into their professional well-being. Notably, teachers aged 41-50 constitute the largest group, emphasizing the importance of recognizing diverse experiences across different age brackets. Additionally, a significant gender disparity exists, with females comprising the majority, underscoring the need for investigations into gender dynamics in the profession. Career stage breakdown shows a predominance of proficient educators, highlighting the blend of experience levels within the workforce. Despite high levels of efficacy and satisfaction, there is room for improvement in handling disruptive behavior and enriching extracurricular offerings.

Surprisingly, age groups showed no significant differences in efficacy or satisfaction, suggesting age alone may not dictate these aspects of teacher well-being. However, gender differences are evident, with female teachers reporting significantly higher self-efficacy. Although not statistically significant, they also express slightly higher job satisfaction. Similarly, career stages do not strongly influence self-efficacy or job satisfaction.

3.2. Supportive school culture's effect on teachers' self-efficacy and teachers' job satisfaction

Table 8 presents the results of the multivariate analysis of variance or MANOVA, which was used to examine the impact of a supportive school culture on TSE and job satisfaction. MANOVA was chosen as it allows the analysis of multiple dependent variables simultaneously, making it a suitable method for assessing how supportive school culture influences both outcomes while controlling for potential correlations between them. MANOVA reveals a significant relationship between the studied variables. Supportive school culture was found to have a significant effect on both satisfaction ($F(12, 84)=6.601$, $p<0.001$) and efficacy ($F(12, 84)=14.766$, $p<0.001$). The partial eta squared values were .485 for job satisfaction and 0.678 for efficacy, indicating a large effect size for both variables. These findings suggest that a supportive school

culture plays a crucial role in influencing teachers' satisfaction and efficacy levels. Specifically, the analysis revealed that supportive school culture accounted for 48.5% of the variance in satisfaction and 67.8% of the variance in efficacy. The result is consistent with several findings [18], [22], [24]–[26] that school culture positively influence teachers' satisfaction. Also, it supports research by Schipper *et al.* [20] and Min [21], who claimed that school culture predicts teacher's efficacy.

Table 8. The influence of supportive school culture on teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction

Source	Dependent variable	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.	Partial eta squared
Corrected model	Self-efficacy	10.268 ^a	12	0.856	14.766	0.000	0.678
	Job satisfaction	9.367 ^b	12	0.781	6.601	0.000	0.485
Intercept	Self-efficacy	335.059	1	335.059	5781.956	0.000	0.986
	Job satisfaction	309.365	1	309.365	2615.990	0.000	0.969
Supportive school culture	Self-efficacy	10.268	12	0.856	14.766	0.000	0.678
	Job satisfaction	9.367	12	0.781	6.601	0.000	0.485
Error	Self-efficacy	4.868	84	0.058			
	Job satisfaction	9.934	84	0.118			
Total	Self-efficacy	1303.784	97				
	Job satisfaction	1210.428	97				
Corrected total	Self-efficacy	15.136	96				
	Job satisfaction	19.301	96				

a. R squared=0.678 (adjusted R squared=0.632); b. R squared=0.485 (adjusted R squared=0.412)

4. CONCLUSION

This study offers new insights by concurrently analyzing how educational and personal contexts shape TSE and job satisfaction within a rural Philippines setting—an area less explored in the existing literature. By integrating supportive school culture with personal context variables such as age, gender, and career stage, the research provides a more holistic understanding of teacher well-being. A key contribution lies in confirming the substantial role of a supportive school culture in enhancing both efficacy and satisfaction, with gender emerging as a significant personal factor influencing self-efficacy. These findings underscore the importance of school-based interventions focused on cultivating collaborative, inclusive, and empowering environments.

The study's implications extend to policy and leadership practices, suggesting that educational leaders prioritize building supportive cultures through mentorship, professional development, and gender-sensitive approaches. Although personal factors showed limited influence, the results validate the transformative impact of school culture on teacher motivation and effectiveness. This research fills a gap in the contextual understanding of teacher experiences in underrepresented educational environments, offering a basis for targeted strategies to boost teacher morale and instructional quality. Future studies should expand to broader contexts and adopt longitudinal and qualitative designs to capture evolving dynamics in teacher development.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

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Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Ellaine Joy G. Eusebio	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓				✓	
Philip R. Baldera		✓				✓		✓	✓		✓	✓		
Aljay Marc C. Patiam	✓			✓					✓		✓	✓		
Charton F. Sombria	✓		✓		✓			✓						
Jacel Ruz F. Gan		✓				✓				✓			✓	
Connie G. Castillo	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓		✓	✓

C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author [EJGE], upon reasonable request.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Ellaine Joy G. Eusebio is an associate professor II at Romblon State University (RSU), Philippines. She is teaching at the College of Business and Accountancy and is the current associate dean of the Graduate Education and Professional Studies at RSU. She holds a postgraduate diploma in management and a master of business administration from De La Salle University, Manila, and is currently pursuing a Ph.D. in business at the same institution. Her research interests include strategic human resource management, educational leadership and management, and consumer behavior. She is also actively involved in community extension projects and has served as a resource speaker in various entrepreneurial, financial literacy, and educational leadership and management programs. She can be contacted at email: eusebioellainejoy@rsu.edu.ph.

Philip R. Baldera is an associate professor V at Romblon State University and the current dean of Graduate Education and Professional Studies. He earned his doctor of philosophy in Educational Leadership and Management from The National Teachers College, Manila, and his master of arts in education from Eulogio "Amang" Rodriguez Institute of Science and Technology. With extensive experience in educational leadership, he has published several research papers on topics including outcome-based education, computational thinking, and strategic management. Dr. Baldera is also a distinguished speaker and facilitator in national and international conferences and actively engages in community service and educational capacity-building initiatives. He can be contacted at email: philipbaldera001@gmail.com.

Aljay Marc C. Patiam is an assistant professor III at Romblon State University and the current Director of the Laboratory Science High School (LSHS). He earned his doctor of philosophy in Educational Leadership and Management at Romblon State University - Odiongan and is currently pursuing a doctor of philosophy in science education at the University of Perpetual Help System Dalta. With years of experience in school leadership, Dr. Patiam has published research papers focused on education, teaching strategies, and school management. He also serves as a speaker and facilitator in various local and international seminars and conferences, sharing his expertise in the field of education. He can be contacted at email: patiamaljaymarc@gmail.com.

Charton F. Sombria is an assistant professor IV at Romblon State University, currently serving under the College of Business and Accountancy. With 16 years of teaching experience—7 years as a lecturer and 9 years as a regular faculty member—she is a licensed professional teacher who believes that education is a lifelong and evolving journey. She earned her master's degree in education, major in English, from Romblon State University and completed her bachelor's degree in mass communication at Far Eastern University, Manila. Passionate about teaching and community engagement, she actively participates in the university's extension programs and serves as a resource speaker and facilitator. Her involvement in both research and outreach reflects her commitment to making education meaningful, responsive, and relevant to the changing needs of learners and society. She can be contacted at email: callhercharton@gmail.com.

Jacel Ruz F. Gan is an instructor III at Romblon State University, specializing in English as a second language (ESL). With years of teaching experience at both secondary and college levels, she is committed to creating a supportive and engaging learning environment. A licensed professional teacher and holder of a master of arts in Education major in ESL, Jacel brings strong communication skills, creativity, and leadership to her role as an educator. She is also active as a tutor and proofreader, helping learners enhance their English proficiency. She can be contacted at email: jacelalesha@gmail.com.

Connie G. Castillo is an accomplished educator currently serving as a teacher III in the Department of Education, Division of Romblon, under the District of Looc. She earned her master's degree in educational management from Romblon State University and her bachelor of elementary education, specializing in home economics, from Romblon State College. She also holds a vocational certificate in office management with computer from Romblon College. With over 18 years of teaching experience, she has demonstrated unwavering commitment to quality education. She can be contacted at email: castilloconnie128@gmail.com.